

THE IMPORTANCE OF CONSERVING THE BIODIVERSITY IN FAMILY GARDENS FOR IMPROVING FOOD SECURITY, IN CONTEXT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Iuliana ALUPEI

Centre of Mountain Economy “CE-MONT”, Național Institute for Mountain
Biotechnology, Petreni, nr. 49, 725700, Vatra Dornei, Jud. Suceava, România
E-mail: *iulianamorariu11@yahoo.com*

Abstract

The current pandemic context generated by COVID-19 and the rapid mode of transmission and evolution of the virus have highlighted the importance of addressing a healthy lifestyle through a balanced diet. Under the insolation conditions imposed by the authorities to reduce the risk of disease transmission, an important role was played by gardening practices, which contributed to the well-being of the population, especially in rural areas, where gardens have become an important element in food production and the creation of recreation spaces. This paper is based on the bibliographic study of the importance of family gardens, with the purpose of highlighting their value. These gardens of small sizes have various social, economical and environmental benefits and have played, traditionally, an important role in food production and maintaining biodiversity. Family gardens are also an important element in mountainous regions, these areas being considered fragile, characterized by fragmented parts of land, limited in terms of mechanization by the slopes and altitude, because it contributes to landscape modeling and ensures the production of quality food in small areas.

Keywords: *COVID-19, family gardens, healthy eating, biodiversity, mountain area.*

INTRODUCTION

Factors such as biodiversity loss, climate change, malnutrition, changing the way of using the land and most recently, the COVID-19 pandemic have highlighted the importance of agriculture and food production (Szobo, 2016).

In any ecosystem, biodiversity plays an important role, as it acts and improves environmental sustainability. The concept of biodiversity involves the rural landscape, where local species interact with each other, to which environmental characteristics also contribute.

Worldwide, genetic resources have suffered heavy loss, according to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO, 2004; FAO, 2010). As for the global biodiversity, about 75% has been lost in the last century, and worldwide three-quarters of food is produced by only twelve species of plants and five species of animals (FAO, 2004; Escuinias, 2010). Both researchers and politicians have highlighted the importance of conserving crop genetic resources in their original environment (Maxted, Guarino and Chiwona, 2002). The researchers have focused on the “*in situ*” conservation of biological resources, in order to maintain and restore the variety of the species in the natural environment from which they come (Altieri and Merrick, 1987). In order to obtain new varieties, local varieties are the most genetically suitable for cultivation in organic systems, which are increasingly common.

In this context, the development of mountain areas has also been subject to the pressure of climate change and the use of natural resources. In Romania, the rural population is

economically dependent on agriculture, this being the main activity. Over 50% of the agricultural production is used for own consumption (Tudor, 2015). Rural mountain areas are characterized as disadvantaged by the definition adopted in Article 18 of Regulation (EC) No 1257/99, which are prone to erosion and landslides, and agricultural practices can help to restore land, thereby reducing erosion agents (rains, floods, precipitations), and by cultivation, the nutrients in the soil are retained (Ives, 2004). This previous definition has led to the depopulation of mountainous territories and the decline of agriculture over time (MacDonald et al., 2000).

However, for mountain areas, climate change plays an important role, as global warming can expand the area of vegetable planting in mountain regions at increasing levels (Yao et al., 2017). The average global temperature during the last century has increased by 0.74°C, and according to forecasts can increase by 1.1–6.4°C by the end of the century (Solomon, 2007). Home gardens (HG) in mountain areas can help shape landscapes and at the same time provide vital services such as biodiversity conservation, the provision of fresh vegetables and fruits, the formation of recreation areas. A main condition for survival in the specific conditions of mountain areas, is to adapt and accept the challenges, so as to support the ecological, social and cultural patterns (Crowley, 2013).

The pandemic period of COVID-19 also had a major influence on the world's population. Millions of people live close to poverty, due to lack of economic means, supply disruptions and rising food prices. Like any other pandemic, it has caused significant changes in society (Blay-Palmer et al., 2020), directly affecting health, quality of life, food security and last but not least, financial security (Gruère and Brooks, 2021).

Currently, the existing problems caused by the pandemic, climate change and the loss of genetic resources have led to an approach to the development of traditional local agriculture, emphasizing the importance of local supply chains.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology applied in this paper is based on the analysis of the specialized literature, by evaluating the bibliographic references regarding the research topic approached. In order to elaborate the proposed objectives, various articles and specialized studies were consulted through the search engine “Web of science”, and the main keywords used were “home garden”, “food security”, “mountain agriculture”, “biodiversity”.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

During the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, it was recommended that the World Health Organization adopt a healthy lifestyle that could contribute to the prevention and treatment of the disease (WHO, 2020). The pandemic period revealed one of the major problems related to food insecurity facing the world's population, and with the restrictions measures, vulnerable parts of society suffered. An additional mechanism that supported food supply was the implementation of short circuits to address food resilience issues (Bakalis et al., 2020). An important role in this context was also played by the gardens around the houses, which in addition to appearance (Cameron and Blanuša, 2016), are also important motivations for the consumption of fresh and organic food and gardening itself as a hobby (Smith and Jehlička,

2013). This development of community-supported agriculture can have a favorable influence on healthy local products (Bakalis et al., 2020). The changes that occur in the economy and the increase of demographic pressures, fuel the concern for gardens and the genetic content they contain. Agriculture practiced at a large scale, globally, leads to a simplification of natural agricultural systems and landscapes, producing soil erosion over time (Biol, Bela and Smale, 2005).

All over the globe, millions of people live close to poverty, due to lack of economic means, supply disruptions and rising food prices. The world's population has come to consume more and more processed foods, with fresh fruits and vegetables being less available or more expensive in stores. Highly processed foods have a negative influence on health, and on people with diabetes, non-communicable diseases that require diet, become a risk factor for mortality caused by COVID-19 (IPES-Food, 2020). These effects are the result of global urbanization and modern agricultural practices that have led to the formation of complex food supply chains, which face long-distance transportation of raw materials, declining quality (Bakalis et al., 2020).

The world's population by 2050 is estimated to reach over 9 billion, so there is a continuing need to increase food production and make stocks for growing demand. More than half a billion people around the world are currently suffering from food insecurity, and it is clear that resources for food production are becoming less and less expensive. The effort to innovate in agriculture is increasingly deficient, due to the degradation of natural resources and climate change (Galhena, Freed and Maredia, 2013).

A universal concern remains food security which results in an adverse effect on well-known external factors: land use change, globalization, climate change (Misselhorn et al., 2012), and most recently, the pandemic created by the Sars-Cov-2 virus. The concept of food crisis is closely linked to the economic, social, ecological, and political crises. The notion of hunger has been redefined, because in the past it was geographically located, and after the phenomenon of globalization it was felt in low-income groups. This food crisis has made its global presence felt by rising prices (Brown, 2005). The diversity of agricultural systems plays an important role in supporting global food security (Hajjar, Jarvis and Gemmill-Herren, 2008). During the pandemic period of COVID-19, a stress factor was the interruption of supply, which triggered a state of panic and subsequent disruption of local supply chains (Lewis, 2020). In this context of food security, several approaches to population intervention have been proposed (e.g., Schipper and Langston, 2015; Serfilippi and Raminath, 2018), with research using the household as an analysis (e.g., D'Errico, Romano and Pietrelli, 2018).

The continuous deterioration of natural resources and ecosystems for both food production and the environment has become a major problem (Balana, Mathijs and Muys, 2010). Although the loss of biodiversity has many causes, the main ones can be conventional agriculture and the growing population, so for the improvement of biodiversity, it is important to approach agricultural practices (Musotsi, Sigor and Onyango, 2008), in HG (home gardens).

The gathered information focused on HG, because in the current context their importance was highlighted, especially in maintaining genetic resources (Agelet, Bonet and Vallés, 2000), slowing climate change, and stability of food security (Mbow et al., 2014). The literature emphasizes that family gardens in many developing countries are part of agricultural food production systems, and are widely used as a remedy for hunger (Johnson et al., 2000) and production. Increasingly beneficial to health, HGs are an element of cultural identity, as local

traditions and culture are closely linked to agricultural activities in the region (Calvet-Mir et al., 2011), and the consumption of products provided by small farms have played an important role against poverty, of all times (Tudor, 2015) and quality food production appears as the most appreciated service in these gardens (Sandhu, Wratten and Cullen, 2010). For rural livelihoods, the significance of family gardens is highly valued worldwide (Fernandes and Nair, 1986; Jose and Shanmugaratnam, 1993; Nair, 2006). In some cultures, gardening is very popular, for example, in the UK it is estimated that 49% of the adult population participates in these activities (Department of Cultural and Sports Media, 2017). In the US, it is similarly estimated that 78% of homeowners regularly participate in gardening (Kiesling and Manning, 2010). In Romania, the rural population is economically dependent on agriculture, this being the main activity. Of agricultural production, over 50% are used for own consumption (Tudor, 2015). Agriculture, which contributes to the protection of the landscape and supports economic development (MacDonald et al., 2000), is also essential for slowing down migration and abandoning land in mountainous areas. In the European Alps, agriculture is based on family contribution, and in addition to providing a livelihood and helping to shape the land, it is also appreciated for recreational and tourist uses (Flury, Huber and Tasser, 2013).

HGs refer to small areas of land, which are found in the vicinity of households (Odebode, 2016), being described as mixed crops, which include vegetables, fruits, spices, as well as sources for animal feed (Fresco and Westphal, 1998). Several themes have been used to describe garden production systems, such as: “household garden, mixed garden, backyard garden, garden culture” (Mitchell and Hanstad, 2004), these being generally administered by women, and the resulting products are used for own consumption, occasionally for sale (Furlan, Pochettino and Westphal, 2017). In terms of sustainable development, gardens can serve as places of agrobiodiversity and conservation of traditional plant cultivation (Darby, Hinton and Torre, 2020), and most of the time, even if the diversity of species in home gardens is not the main source of maintenance, they contribute to an important variety in the household diet (Kumar and Nair, 2004). Also, the high density of plants grown in gardens provides an ideal environment for certain species of wild animals, such as birds, small mammals, reptiles, and insects (Thin et al., 2003).

A potential benefit of mountain gardens is the reduction of soil erosion and land conservation (Soemarwoto, 1987). This reduction in erosion is associated with a decrease in soil organic matter losses, thus maintaining increased fertility. Compared to conventional systems, where landscape elements are removed for mechanization, cultivation in small areas preserves landscape components, which contribute to water retention in the soil, reduce the risk of floods and drought, and carbon is retained in the plant’s biomass and the soil (Benton, Vickery and Wilson, 2003). The recommended strategies for restoring degraded land are ecological agricultural practices that are characterized by the application of organic fertilizers, crops, and their rotation (Blanco-Canqui and Lal, 2010). Organic matter is added by administering manure from animals and poultry, which adds the content of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium to the soil (Powell and Williams, 1993).

It is important to support cultivation on individual plots for sustainability, thus significantly reducing carbon emissions from transport, packaging, high water consumption, and chemicals used for food production (Fletcher et al., 2013). In Europe, interest in organic farming has grown considerably, evolving from current systems (Navarrette, 2009) and the focus has been on producing quality food and maintaining the environment and resources (Campanelli and Canali, 2012). These methods of organic horticulture are required by certain

practices of vegetable production, in general, higher environmental sustainability due to resource recycling, minimal use of pollutants (Raviv, 2010). Home gardening has a dynamic role in the family diet, as it complements the diet with vegetables and fruits that are rich in vitamins, proteins (Marsh, 1998).

Since the origins of agriculture, food plants from spontaneous flora have been included in human nutrition as a staple food, ingredients of normal diets or an alternative in situations of lack of food (Rigat et al., 2016), as an integrated part of agricultural systems traditional (Johns and Sthapit, 2004). These current changes in local food systems have led to the deterioration of traditional food systems in the mountain area, thus leading to an increased risk of food security and nutrition (Rasul et al., 2018). In Europe there are still many locations that use plants from spontaneous flora in a traditional way, as remedies (Fierascu et al., 2017). In Central and Eastern Europe are used berries such as *Morus alba*, *Sorbus domestica*, and *Sorbus torminalis*, and in Slovakia (Dénes et al., 2012) bulbs of *Allium scorodoprasum*. A new phenomenon associated with wild food plants, known in industrialized countries as a new trend in nutrition and healthy eating is the transformation of these plants into culinary specialties (Reyes-Garcia et al., 2015).

CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this paper was to highlight the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic in parallel with existing stressors, such as climate change, natural disasters, economic and political disturbances, degradation of natural resources, all of which have an effect on food security. The pandemic context can be a trigger to pay more attention to food production, especially in family gardens, which have many benefits, as evidenced by the literature. The study on literature supports the promotion of HG, for the improvement of the food system, by practicing organic and sustainable agriculture. Following the existing threats, which are mainly aimed at a global food crisis, the emphasis has been on improving local food production systems, to which species of spontaneous flora also contribute.

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